

The Basics of Urban Photography

When you're shooting in an urban environment, it's easy to get tunnel vision and miss out on the best shots. The following are some tips and tricks by [San Francisco-based photographer](#) Har Kwan Luk to help you take better photos in the city.

Making the Shot

The first step to making better photos is to make sure you're prepared. You need to have your camera ready and gear set up, but more importantly, you need to know what you want. What are the specific shots that you want from the day? What will your photo look like at its end? Make a plan, if it's not clear in your head, don't take the shot.

#1: Know Your Location

If it's your first time shooting in an urban setting, Har Kwan Luk suggests trying to get there early for scouting purposes. Get a feel for where light is coming from and where the best spots are for photoshoots. This should help you decide where to place your subject so that they have good light on them and will be easily recognizable when captured by your lens.

#2: Consider Your Subject

[Har Kwan Luk](#) recommends making sure that you're taking pictures of something interesting or relevant to what you're trying to capture. If they're just standing around while talking on their phone (which many people do), then they probably won't be a focal point of your photos.

Composition

The best tip by Har Kwan Luk for getting the perfect shot is composition. You should always strive to place your subject in the center of the frame and make sure that your subjects are well lit. This will help create a dramatic image.

Another thing you can do to improve your composition is to use foreground elements and props in your shots. These props can be anything from signs, statues, or a flower pot. By adding these foreground elements into your shot, you'll be able to draw the viewer's eye towards them and thus creating a more interesting image.

Editing Your Photos

Editing your photos is an important step in the process of making great urban photos. [Skilled photographer](#) Har Kwan Luk indicates that it can help you get rid of unwanted elements and highlight what's most important.

For example, if you're shooting a cityscape, you might want to stop down your aperture so that the focus is on the buildings rather than

lights. This will also make it easier for people to appreciate what's happening in the scene: instead of just seeing a blurry mess of light, they'll be able to see the landscape and its details. Another thing you can do is adjust your exposure settings so that your image has a more dramatic feel. By doing this, you'll be able to show off all the hard work you put into editing your photos!